

Urban Revitalization through Transportation Systems

Revitalização urbana a partir dos sistemas de transportes
Revitalización Urbana a través de los Sistemas de Transporte

Recebido
Received
Recibido
03 jul. 2025
Jul. 03, 2025
03 jul. 2025

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado
24 ago. 2025
Aug. 24, 2025
24 ago. 2025

Publicado
Published
Publicado
01 out. 2025
Oct. 01, 2025
01 oct. 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.5281/zenodo.20146474

São Paulo

v. 4 | n. 1
v. 4 | i. 1

e41357

Outubro/Dezembro
October/December
Octubre/Diciembre

2025

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Abstract:

This study aimed to present a proposal for the utilization of urban spaces based on the existing transportation infrastructure along Avenida Doutor Ricardo Jafet, located in the Cursino district, southeastern São Paulo. The proposal involves the implementation of a bus station beneath the viaduct crossing the avenue, with integrated access to the Santos-Imigrantes station on the Green Line of the São Paulo Metro. Project development included the creation of design sketches using AutoCAD 2020 software, taking into account the intermodal connections and the spatial configuration of the surrounding area. The findings indicated the feasibility of the proposal by highlighting its potential to contribute to urban reorganization through the introduction of mobility-oriented structures aimed at serving the local population.

Keywords: Terminal design; Structural repurposing; Transport systems; Urban mobility.

Resumo:

O objetivo deste estudo foi apresentar proposta para o aproveitamento de espaços urbanos com base na infraestrutura de transportes existente na avenida doutor Ricardo Jafet, na região do cursino, sudeste da cidade de São Paulo, por meio da implantação de uma estação de ônibus sob o viaduto transversal a via, com acessos integrados à estação Santos-imigrantes da linha verde do metrô. Para o desenvolvimento do projeto, foram elaborados croquis utilizando o *software* AutoCAD 2020, considerando a articulação entre os modais e a configuração do entorno. Os resultados indicaram a viabilidade da proposta ao apontar o potencial de reorganização urbana por meio da introdução de estruturas voltadas à mobilidade e atendimento da população.

Palavras-chave: Projeto de terminais; Aproveitamento de estruturas; Sistemas de Transportes; Mobilidade urbana.

Resumen:

El objetivo de este estudio fue presentar una propuesta para el aprovechamiento de espacios urbanos a partir de la infraestructura de transporte existente en la Avenida Doctor Ricardo Jafet, en la región del Cursino, zona sudeste de la ciudad de São Paulo, mediante la implementación de una estación de autobuses bajo el viaducto que cruza dicha vía, con accesos integrados a la estación Santos-Imigrantes de la Línea Verde del metro. Para el desarrollo del proyecto, se elaboraron croquis utilizando el software AutoCAD 2020, considerando la articulación entre los modos de transporte y la configuración del entorno. Los resultados indicaron la viabilidad de la propuesta

al señalar su potencial para la reorganización urbana mediante la incorporación de estructuras orientadas a la movilidad y al servicio de la población.

Palabras clave: *Diseño de terminales; Reutilización de estructuras; Sistemas de transporte; Movilidad urbana.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of life in urban centers depends directly on the organization of public services, specifically public transportation systems, whose function extends beyond physical displacement to influence access to opportunities, health, and social interaction. Urban mobility, as a condition for accessible and adequate movement, sustains the right to the city by promoting inclusion and reducing inequalities. Deficiencies in infrastructure and services compromise this access, exacerbating socio-spatial disparities and requiring actions that promote urban justice and sustainability (Alvim, Izaga and Claps, 2018). Public transportation shapes the dynamics of metropolises, directly influencing how urban spaces are used and appropriated (Araújo et al., 2011).

Brazilian cities present different consequences stemming from the degradation of the urban environment, resulting from both the way the territory is occupied and the organization of the transport system, creating gaps in urban planning and in the sustainable management of urban spaces (Decastro, Saldanha, Balassiano, 2017). Moving around the city presents varied problems depending on the starting point and destination, as urban travel is influenced by factors such as distance, availability of public transport, congestion, road infrastructure, cycle paths, and adequate sidewalks (Carvalho, 2023).

Road complexes, viaducts, railway lines, and areas near large urban facilities frequently interrupt the landscape, isolate regions, and compromise integration with the surroundings, resulting in the underutilization of large territorial areas, marked by insecurity and abandonment. These structures create physical barriers that hinder circulation, devalue urban space, and weaken the local social and economic fabric, contributing to processes of community degradation (Jacobs, 2007). Cities in various countries have redeveloped these previously degraded areas beneath viaducts and transport stations, transforming them into places for leisure, social interaction, sports, and events, thereby helping reconnect neighborhoods previously isolated by these structures (SOMOS CIDADE, 2025).

The urban infrastructure of São Paulo, comprising bridges, viaducts, subways, trains, and bus stations, shapes mobility dynamics and influences the city's form, promoting connections but also fragmentation and urban voids. The implementation of subway stations at different levels directly affects adjacent areas, potentially creating both active hubs and neglected spaces. Over time, viaducts have contributed to urban growth but have also created physical and social barriers, revealing their impact on the organization of the territory. The presence of railway and road lines in central areas intensifies the emergence of vacant land, whose requalification represents a strategic challenge for the reintegration and revitalization of the urban fabric (Amozou, 2000; Vasconcellos, 2001).

The revitalization of urban voids, such as spaces under viaducts, offers an alternative for requalifying degraded areas and improving the urban experience by converting them into spaces for social interaction and the delivery of public services. Frequently neglected and associated with deterioration, these locations

are transformed into areas intended for terminals integrated with shopping centers, cultural facilities, or social support units, promoting diverse and socially inclusive uses (Maia; Leonelli, 2020). The use of these structures as qualified occupations contributes to enhancing the landscape, preserving collective memory and reducing feelings of insecurity by establishing links to public safety (Santos, 2020). Initiatives that combine mobility and commercial activities, such as connections among bus terminals, metro stations, and service centers, demonstrate the potential of these spaces to expand urban vitality and optimize land use, thus fostering a more accessible and safer city (Amaral; Cadore, 2019).

Several initiatives in Brazil and abroad demonstrate that requalifying underutilized urban spaces can transform the landscape and promote collective, inclusive uses. In Brazil, the Galeria dos Estados Viaduct in Brasília underwent a retrofit based on structural, environmental, and functional criteria, reintegrating it into daily urban life. In São Paulo, the "Baixo Viaduto" project allocated areas beneath viaducts for cultural and social activities, encouraging active use and a sense of security. In Zaragoza, Spain, the "Esto no es un solar" program converted vast areas of vacant land into gardens, parks, and sports areas, strengthening active mobility and citizen participation. In Paris, the Porte de Clignancourt was transformed into a multifunctional space focused on urban integration, while Medellín, Colombia, linked escalators and cable cars to public transport, connecting isolated communities and promoting social inclusion through spatial restructuring and improved access.

The objective was to present a proposal for the reuse of existing structures on Avenida Doutor Ricardo Jafet, in the Cursino neighborhood, to implement transfer or integration stations between modes of transport, using the Santos-Imigrantes metro station as a reference. The proposal leverages the site's strategic location to reorganize urban flows and expand access to public services, directly addressing urban fragmentation and improving quality of life. By enabling more efficient mobility and transforming underused spaces, the project is significant for advancing sustainable urban development practices and enhancing social cohesion in rapidly growing cities. The study's justification is based on Sustainable Development Goal No. 11 of the United Nations, which addresses sustainable cities and communities, given that improving mobility conditions directly affects the population's quality of life.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Forms of urban intervention

Urban renewal refers to large-scale interventions that profoundly transform the structure of cities, replacing old buildings with new structures that serve modern economic functions and distinct morphologies, often geared towards high-value business and financial activities. This transformation alters the urban form, the local economic base, and the social composition of territories, resulting in the reoccupation of city centers by multinational companies and the displacement of residents and activities with lower purchasing power to peripheral areas. Consequently, structural changes occur in the morphological, functional, and

social dimensions, characterized by a new urban landscape, the replacement of economic functions, and the displacement of populations with distinct socioeconomic profiles (Moura et al., 2006; Moreira, 2012; Vargas; Castilho, 2015; Lima, 2017).

Urban rehabilitation involves adapting degraded areas without completely destroying the existing urban fabric, prioritizing the preservation and enhancement of residential use through improvements in habitability, infrastructure, services, and the quality of public space. Unlike renovation, it involves selective interventions in buildings, including restorations, renovations, or even partial demolitions, as well as in the urban landscape, reinforcing facades and communal spaces. The process values social participation, coordination among stakeholders, and solutions such as temporary relocation, especially in historical centers, whose preservation contributes to sustainable development by avoiding excessive consumption of land and non-renewable resources, as well as mitigating ecological impacts associated with mass demolition and reconstruction (Moura et al., 2006; Moreira, 2012; Vargas; Castilho, 2015; Lima, 2017).

Urban redevelopment aims to improve living conditions by constructing or restoring infrastructure and facilities, and enhancing public spaces, consequently promoting social and economic dynamics that restore accessibility and attractiveness to degraded urban areas. This strategy alters the value of territories by encouraging economic activities with higher financial returns, cultural uses, and the production of public spaces with symbolic and functional relevance. With a strong strategic character, it acts as a catalyst for territorial transformations, guiding new patterns of urban use and organization, focusing on economic performance and urban integration (Moura et al., 2006; Moreira, 2012; Vargas; Castilho, 2015; Lima, 2017).

Urban promotion serves as strategic support for the revitalization of urban areas by mobilizing economic, institutional, and social efforts, starting with marketing, fundraising, and building economic foundations for projects. Essential for public acceptance and the sustainability of interventions, it involves continuous communication of progress, consensus-building, and encouragement of collective participation, hence consolidating urban governance practices. Thus, its function focuses on articulating management, visibility, and social engagement, using tools such as territorial branding and policies to enhance the urban image and strengthen transformation processes (Moura et al., 2006; Moreira, 2012; Vargas; Castilho, 2015; Lima, 2017).

The analysis of recent revitalization, rehabilitation, and requalification projects in degraded urban areas requires attention to local dynamics and global political, economic, and social changes of the last two decades. Although these changes began in developed countries, they have also affected peripheries and semi-peripheries, thereby disseminating these interventions. Such projects, carried out in diverse contexts, demonstrate benefits including investment in the restoration of architectural heritage, economic valorization through tourism, encouragement of urban conservation, and increased public recognition of these areas. However, they face criticism regarding the concentration of resources in

restricted areas, the social exclusion generated by market logic, the limitation of residents' participation in decision-making, cultural decharacterization, and selectivity in heritage preservation, frequently defined by the interests of economic and institutional agents linked to cultural and tourism promotion (Köhler, 2008).

2.2 Urbanistic influences on the formation of the city of São Paulo

Five urban planning currents have influenced city planning worldwide: Garden Cities, Modernism, New Urbanism, Cities for People, and the 15-Minute City. The first, conceived by Ebenezer Howard, proposed autonomous circular districts uniting the countryside and the city, with defined zones and a green belt. Modernism, notably through Le Corbusier and the Bauhaus, prioritized functionalism and rigid zoning, influencing works such as Brasília. New Urbanism, led by Peter Calthorpe, Andres Duany, Elizabeth Plater-Zyberk, and other founders, reacted to urban sprawl by prioritizing human scale, mixed land use, and attractive public spaces. Jan Gehl, with his proposal for Cities for People, advocated for walkable, sensory, and vibrant neighborhoods, planned for interaction and well-being, and criticized car-centric urbanism. Carlos Moreno conceived the 15-Minute City, which proposes urban reorganization around the proximity between housing, work, education, health, and leisure, reducing commutes and strengthening community ties (SOMOS CIDADE, 2022).

The urban design of São Paulo at the beginning of the 20th century reflected the intense circulation of European and North American urban planning ideas, influencing Brazilian professionals trained in those countries and manifesting itself in improvements to the city center, the control and direction of growth, and the diffusion of the anti-metropolis concept. The engineer Victor Silva Freire, trained in Lisbon and Paris, distinguished himself by directing public works and incorporating influences from urban planners such as Camillo Sitte and Barry Parker, applying them in plans such as the 1911 plan and in the regulations that enabled garden suburbs. Other urban planners, such as Prestes Maia and Anhaia Mello, also contributed to the implementation of these ideas; the latter emphasized the containment of urban growth, zoning, and well-being, drawing on the work of Patrick Geddes and Lewis Mumford, and worked in academia and urban planning institutions. These pioneers were fundamental in incorporating foreign concepts into São Paulo's urban planning, disseminating them within public bodies and academic environments, shaping national urban planning thought, and offering an important contribution to the historical understanding of the circulation of ideas in the context of the global south (Cantarim, 2020).

The urban development of São Paulo was influenced by road plans, such as the 1930 Avenues Plan, which proposed a ring road and radial avenues to mitigate congestion and reorganize traffic, although only the road infrastructure was implemented. This intervention boosted verticalization and the expansion of the city center, transforming it into a financial and commercial hub. However, from the 1960s onwards, the negative effects of the road-centric model became evident, with increased congestion, pollution, and a concentration of investments in the southwest, which functionally weakened the center. Works such as the Costa e Silva Elevated Highway, despite attempting to improve traffic,

fragmented the urban fabric and aggravated the decline of the central area, which, even with the implementation of the subway and urban renewal initiatives, did not recover its primacy, as investments migrated to other regions such as Avenida Paulista, Faria Lima, and Marginal Pinheiros. Thus, the road plans that emerged in response to accelerated growth ended up reinforcing spatial inequalities and promoting economic decentralization, thereby consolidating the polycentric and unequal configuration of the current metropolis (Sant'anna, 2017).

Currently, São Paulo faces a tension between two distinct urban planning visions: social and sustainable urbanism, which values the requalification of public spaces for pedestrians and cyclists, the inclusion of vulnerable groups, environmental solutions, and citizen participation, such as the transformation of urban structures into parks and community spaces; and car-centric urbanism, still present in public management, which prioritizes the automobile through the creation of parking spaces in areas previously intended for pedestrians and prohibitions on sustainable verticalization, measures that increase inequality, discourage public transportation, and disregard socio-environmental impacts (Back; Malheiros, 2022).

3. METHOD

The study adopted a qualitative approach with an exploratory, descriptive, and methodological character, using technical procedures involving AutoCAD 2020. The Google Earth platform was integrated with AutoCAD 2020 to identify the location and analyze the suitability of the space for the proposed intervention, enabling graphical representation of the intervention proposal and evaluation of its coherence with the characteristics of the surrounding area.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Avenida Doutor Ricardo Jafet, located in the city of São Paulo, was chosen for this study due to its importance as a connecting axis between several districts, such as Cambuci, Mooca, Liberdade, Ipiranga, Vila Mariana, Saúde, Sacomã, Vila Prudente, and Jabaquara, in addition to being part of the Rodovia dos Imigrantes highway that connects the capital to the coast. Starting at Praça do Monumento in Ipiranga, it crosses areas with heavy traffic, such as the surroundings of the Santos-Imigrantes Station on Metro Line 2-Green, and provides access to important arterial roads, including Avenida dos Bandeirantes, the Pinheiros and Tietê Marginal highways, and Avenida do Estado. The avenue also connects points of interest such as the São Paulo Zoo, the São Paulo Expo, and the ABC Paulista region. The channeled Ipiranga stream runs beneath its structure, and it is currently named for Ricardo Nami Jafet, having previously been known as Avenida Tereza Cristina and Avenida Água Funda. Its history is deeply intertwined with the city's urbanization and expansion, reflecting São Paulo's social and economic transformations throughout the centuries.

Avenida Doutor Ricardo Jafet is one of São Paulo's main thoroughfares, playing a significant role in the movement of people and goods. Along its length, it offers

a variety of services, including supermarkets, gas stations, motels, car dealerships, and shopping centers, making it a consumer hub. From the 2000s onwards, the region underwent verticalization and real estate expansion, marked by the construction of residential developments aimed at middle- and upper-class segments, which altered its socioeconomic profile.

Ricardo Jafet Avenue has a history marked by recurring interventions focused on urban infrastructure, mainly due to flooding of the Ipiranga stream, which is channeled along its length. Between 1986 and 2011, at least 11 large-scale flood control works were carried out, totaling more than R\$ 115 million in public funds. The inauguration of the Santos-Imigrantes Station in 2006 expanded the avenue's connectivity to the metro system and facilitated the daily commute of thousands of people. In 2013, the Vila Mariana Subprefecture promoted landscaping improvements by installing gardens in the central median as part of an urban requalification process.

The proposal consists of integrating the Santos-Imigrantes station on the green line of the metro with a new transfer terminal linking metro-rail and road passenger transport, using the viaduct near the station. The proposal foresees implementing the structure on Rua Saioá in the Cursino district to enable functional connectivity between transport systems and expand capacity to meet the region's mobility demands.

Figure 1 - Spatial insertion of the locality

Source: Google Earth (2025).

Initially, Figure 2 presents an overview of the project, in which the lower part of Avenida Doutor Ricardo Jafet is designated for the installation of the bus station, with underground access planned as a solution to ensure the circulation of pedestrians and passengers without the need to build new viaducts or elevated walkways, respecting the existing urban configuration and optimizing the use of available infrastructure.

Figure 2 - Project overview

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 3 below shows an aerial view of the station, whose design incorporates the pure geometric forms characteristic of the aesthetics of São Paulo architect João Artacho Jurado, prioritizing structural solutions and the minimalist use of materials. Superfluous decorative elements were eliminated from the configuration and finishes, while the roof features openwork components that allow for greater use of natural lighting, contributing to the rationalization of energy consumption.

Figure 3 - Aerial view of the station

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 4 shows the access points to the station via Avenida Doutor Ricardo Jafet, with entrances and underground passages that ensure the safe and integrated circulation of users within the urban context.

Figure 4 - Station access

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 5 shows a cross-section of the existing structures and the proposed new structure, demonstrating the articulation between the elements already in place and the planned interventions, with a focus on the functional integration of the whole.

Figure 5 - Articulation between existing structures and the proposed new structure.

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 6 shows the connection between the Santos-Imigrantes metro station, the connecting walkway between stations, and the proposed intermodal station, spatially organizing the elements that comprise the integration system between the modes of transport.

Figure 6 - Representation of the interconnection between stations

Source: The authors (2025).

Finally, Figure 7 presents the integration plan between the modes of transport.

Figure 7 - Integration plan between modes of transport

Source: The authors (2025).

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study presented a proposal for the use of urban spaces, with a focus on transportation infrastructure, in São Paulo. Initially, an analysis of the urbanistic influences that shaped the city's development was presented. Following this, the project was presented with visual representations from different perspectives to facilitate the spatial interpretation of the proposal and its integration into the analyzed urban context.

The study's results point to a favorable outlook for the project's implementation in the region, indicating that the proposal allows for integration into the urban landscape through targeted interventions with minimal impact on existing structures, while respecting the characteristics of the built environment.

As a suggestion for future research, it is recommended to simulate similar projects on other avenues in the city, prioritizing urban mobility, the connection between different modes of transport, the use of existing structures, and the rational use of available resources.

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